

An Atlas of The Forty Colleges of Education in Ghana

Dr Björn Haßler

REAL Centre, University of Cambridge, UK

Jacob Tetteh Akunor

National Council for Tertiary Education, Ghana

Enock Seth Nyamador

OpenStreetMap Ghana

v1.3

December 2017

Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike

<http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>

Document citation

Please use the following format for citing this document:

Björn Haßler, Jacob Tetteh Akunor, Enock Seth Nyamador (2017). *An Atlas of The Forty Colleges of Education in Ghana*. Available under Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International. Available at <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International

This document is licensed under a Creative Commons licence, that gives you certain rights and obligations. Under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International licence, you are free to:

- **Share** — copy and redistribute the material in any medium or format;
- **Adapt** — remix, transform, and build upon the material for any purpose, even commercially.

The licensor cannot revoke these freedoms as long as you follow the license terms:

- **Attribution** — You must give **appropriate credit**, provide a link to the license, and **indicate if changes were made**. You may do so in any reasonable manner, but not in any way that suggests the licensor endorses you or your use.
- **ShareAlike** — If you remix, transform, or build upon the material, you must distribute your contributions under the **same license** as the original.
- **No additional restrictions** — You may not apply legal terms or **technological measures** that legally restrict others from doing anything the license permits.

Notices:

- You do not have to comply with the license for elements of the material in the public domain or where your use is permitted by an applicable **exception or limitation**.
- No warranties are given. The license may not give you all of the permissions necessary for your intended use. For example, other rights such as [publicity](#), [privacy](#), or [moral rights](#) may limit how you use the material.

For further details, please see <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0>. In particular, the above provides a human-readable summary of (and not a substitute for) the full legal code of the license: <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/legalcode>.

Table of Contents

Introduction	5
How was this atlas produced?	7
The Principles for Digital Development	7
Initial data collection: Locations of the colleges	8
Satellite mapping to add buildings and roads	9
Field mapping to determine college boundaries	9
Mapathons to add buildings and roads	10
Printing PDFs	10
Document assembly	11
Obtaining and using the data in this atlas	12
Using the atlas data on a mobile device	12
Obtaining a copy of this atlas	13
Feedback and future efforts	14
Appendix 1: Attribution	15
Licence for this atlas	15
Contributions via the HOTOSM tasks manager and OSM	15
Other contributions	15
Contributions to Wikipedia	16
Appendix 2: College data	17
Data: College name, region, town, nickname, notes	18
Data: Coordinates, Google Map, OpenStreetMap, OLC	20
Licence for the college data	22
Appendix 3: Overview map of the colleges	23
North of Ghana	24
South of Ghana	25
Licence for the overview map	26
Appendix 4: College maps	27
Licence for the college maps	27
Abetifi Presbyterian College of Education	28
Accra College of Education	30
Ada College of Education	32
Agogo Presbyterian College of Education	34
Akatsi College of Education	36

Akrokerry College of Education	38
Atebubu College of Education	40
Bagabaga College of Education	42
Berekum College of Education	46
Dambai College of Education	48
Enchi College of Education	52
Evangelical Presbyterian College of Education, Amedzofe	54
Evangelical Presbyterian College of Education, Bimbilla	56
Foso College of Education	60
Gambaga College of Education	62
Gbewaa College of Education	64
Holy Child College of Education	66
Jasikan College of Education	68
Kibi Presbyterian College of Education	72
Komenda College of Education	74
Mampong Technical College of Education	76
Mount Mary College of Education	78
Nusrat Jahan Ahmadiyya College of Education	80
Offinso College of Education	82
Our Lady of Apostles College of Education	86
Peki College of Education	90
Presbyterian College of Education, Akropong	92
Presbyterian Women's College of Education, Aburi	94
Seventh Day Adventist College of Education	96
St. Ambrose College of Education	98
St. Francis College of Education	100
St. John Bosco's College of Education	102
St. Joseph's College of Education	104
St. Louis College of Education	106
St. Monica's College of Education	108
St. Teresa's College of Education	110
Tamale College of Education	112
Tumu College of Education	114
Wesley College of Education	118
Wiawso College of Education	122

Introduction

The idea for this atlas arose out of the first author's work as key adviser for the UKAID-funded Transforming Teacher Education and Learning (T-TEL) programme in Ghana. T-TEL had already produced a Google map, but the college locations were only accurate to town-level, and indeed sometimes inaccurate. Naturally, the T-TEL drivers do not all know the exact location of each college, which means that sometimes drivers had to look for colleges. Moreover, each "zone" (see below) was allocated a coach, who would visit each college in turn. Without accurate locations, advance route planning is difficult and overall trips are hard to optimise. It became thus desirable to not only obtain more accurate coordinates, but also to store these in publicly accessible platforms. In the period of the first author's role as key adviser to T-TEL (mid-2015 – end-2016), college coordinates were collected, and added to OpenStreetMap¹ and Google Maps, making the colleges discoverable by anybody and making strategic route planning possible. Using OpenStreetMap data offline (e.g. with the Maps.Me² Android/iOS application) meant that drivers could now also plan routes offline. Moreover, for the first author, collecting the coordinates of the colleges, and looking at the environments of the colleges (rural vs. urban, size, layout) was an additional way of acquainting himself with the colleges.

These ideas of course are not new. Free, up-to-date maps are recognised as a critical resource when relief organizations are responding to disasters or political crises, as evidenced by organisations like Map Action or Missing Maps, and the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap team (HOTOSM). For example, the latter provided maps during hurricanes in the Caribbean, earthquakes in Mexico, a volcano in Bali and flooding in South Asia. Likewise medically focussed research and relief efforts makes extensive use of geospatial data, for example during the Ebola crisis. There is also a culture of sharing data between crisis-focussed organisations; common platforms have been established which enable data sharing and re-use, including HDX³, the HOTOSM exporter⁴, and Health Sites⁵.

In the education sector, however, the use of geospatial data is not as well recognised, and certainly not as visible. For example, while some countries have got databases that provide school locations (alongside other data; e.g. USAID EdAssist in Zambia), many of those databases are not publicly available, and often have not been maintained. Similarly, many NGOs collect their own geospatial data, without sharing this further. While there are some early efforts to coordinate this (School Sites⁶; PROJECT CONNECT⁷US initiative) much work remains to be done.

Within T-TEL, having collected coordinates of the colleges, a further challenge presented itself. As T-TEL progressed towards more detailed planning of ICT in the colleges (throughout 2016), it became clear that only a very small number of colleges had campus

¹ <http://www.openstreetmap.org/>

² <https://maps.me/download/>

³ <https://data.humdata.org/>

⁴ <https://export.hotosm.org/en/v3/>

⁵ <http://healthsites.io>

⁶ <http://schoolsites.io>

⁷ <https://www.projectconnect.world/>

maps. This raised the question how we could accurately plan and cost (for example) WiFi for the college campuses. In October 2016 an ICT survey of the colleges was undertaken by the National Council for Tertiary Education (NCTE, Ghana) with support from T-TEL. The survey was led by the 2nd author. We decided that during this survey, the NCTE also collected basic geospatial information, by asking college members to draw the boundary of the college, as well as label colleges buildings, on existing maps with satellite imagery (see below).

However, as the the first authors key adviser role came to an end in late 2016, it was unclear what would happen with this data, and how it could become useful to support education planning in Ghana. The first two authors decided that we would attempt to process the data in our own time, with view to making the data publicly available. The most efficient route for this seemed to continue using OpenStreetMap to trace buildings and roads within colleges. Because of our involvement with the Humanitarian Street Map team, we also involved a number of volunteers in this process, and started collaborating with the 3rd author. College data was entered into OpenStreetMap throughout 2017, with contributions at several Cambridge-based mapathons with contributions from Ghanaian mappers too.

While the full college data is available through OpenStreetMap, as well as available offline for mobile devices (with Maps.Me), we came to the conclusion that it would be helpful to produce a consolidated, printable atlas, that would raise awareness for the availability of this data.

While a few colleges had plans of their colleges, this atlas is the first comprehensive atlas of all public 40 Colleges of Education. As far as we know, the list presented in this atlas are is most complete and most accurate list of the forty College of Education in existence. This atlas also contains a description of how it was produced, and how it can be maintained.

The atlas was also an opportunity for the first two authors to continue collaborating as colleagues beyond the formal T-TEL programme setting in which they met, as well as to extend the collaboration to include civil society through the third author. We hope that we will have the opportunity to collaborate on many more projects in the future.

We make this atlas available because of our sincere wish to contribute to the development of the education in Ghana and to the wellbeing of the people of Ghana. We hope you find it useful.

Dr Björn Haßler

*REAL Centre,
University of Cambridge, UK*

Jacob Tetteh Akunor

*National Council for Tertiary
Education, Ghana*

Enock Seth Nyamador

OpenStreetMap Ghana

December 2017

How was this atlas produced?

The Principles for Digital Development

There are many different approaches to collecting geospatial data. Our own efforts have been guided by the Principles for Digital Development⁸, which seemed particularly relevant as these have also been endorsed by the UK Department for International Development⁹. The nine principles are:

- **Design With the User.** User-centered design starts with getting to know the people you are designing for through conversation, observation and co-creation.
- **Understand the Existing Ecosystem.** Well-designed initiatives and digital tools consider the particular structures and needs that exist in each country, region and community.
- **Design for Scale.** Achieving scale requires adoption beyond an initiatives pilot population and often necessitates securing funding or partners that take the initiative to new communities or regions.
- **Build for Sustainability.** Building sustainable programs, platforms and digital tools is essential to maintain user and stakeholder support, as well as to maximize long-term impact.
- **Be Data Driven.** When an initiative is data driven, quality information is available to the right people when they need it, and they are using those data to take action.
- **Use Open Standards, Open Data, Open Source, and Open Innovation.** An open approach to digital development can help to increase collaboration in the digital development community and avoid duplicating work that has already been done.
- **Reuse and Improve.** Reusing and improving is about taking the work of the global development community further than any organization or program can do alone.
- **Address Privacy & Security.** Addressing privacy and security in digital development involves careful consideration of which data are collected and how data are acquired, used, stored and shared.

⁸ <https://digitalprinciples.org/>

⁹ Putting digital principles into practice in our aid programmes. Frances Sibbet, Digital Service Lead, 10 November 2015.

<https://dfid.blog.gov.uk/2015/11/10/putting-digital-principles-into-practice-in-our-aid-programmes/>

- **Be Collaborative.** Being collaborative means sharing information, insights, strategies and resources across projects, organizations and sectors, leading to increased efficiency and impact.

For the present atlas, the Principles were used as follows. We **designed with the user and understood the existing ecosystem:** through our prior collaboration between the NCTE and T-TEL, as well as with OSM Ghana, we got to know the actors (e.g. including vehicle drivers, infrastructure planners, etc), as well as existing initiatives and digital tools (such as OSM Ghana’s use of OpenStreetMap). We **design for scale and built for sustainability** by using an existing open, scalable platform (OpenStreetMap), where data will reside for the foreseeable future. We deposited OpenStreetMap data with the NCTE. While our initiative as such was not **data driven**, we collected (and quality assured) our data so that is readily available to those who need it, for example utilising multiple platforms, such as Google maps and OpenStreetMap, as well as offline through Maps.Me¹⁰, an open source application. We used **open standards, open data** hosted in **open source** platforms (i.e. OpenStreetMap). The OpenStreetMap process itself is based on **reuse and iterative improvement**. We did consider **privacy & security** in collecting our data. We aimed to **be collaborative**, working across the organisations of the three authors, immediately shared any collected data (through Google Maps and OpenStreetMap), utilising open licences (Creative Commons Attribution ShareAlike and the Open Database Licence) benefitting from the OpenStreetMap platform and tools increase our efficiency and impact. The font used for the text and tables is the open source Ubuntu font¹¹.

Initial data collection: Locations of the colleges

Initially the available data for the colleges was limited to postal addresses, as well as zones. Some of the the list available to us often contained errors, such as spelling errors. Some colleges were available on Google Maps, while others were available on OpenStreetMap; however, this was often under previous names (e.g. as “teacher training college”, rather than the present name usually involving “college of education”). Also colleges were sometimes referred to by the nicknames or locations, which for those of us new to the Ghanaian colleges, made for a steep learning curve. It thus seemed to be a good idea to start cataloguing the available information.

This cataloguing also included collecting of the geolocations of the colleges. As the authors travelled between colleges, it was simple to collect geolocations by phone. Other geolocations were contributed by colleagues or college staff. This task was by no means trivial, and took several months. Often data had to be corrected. However, we are now satisfied that the data presented in this atlas is indeed accurate, and therefore presents a high value dataset.

The tables in the next section provide

- College name (the full official college name);

¹⁰ <https://github.com/mapsme/omim>

¹¹ <https://design.ubuntu.com/font/>

- Zone (one of the five zones, which appear to be mainly used in education);
- Region
- District / Municipal / Metropolitan;
- Town;
- College name (the usual name, often a slightly abbreviated version of the full name);
- Nickname (the college nickname, usually an abbreviation created from the college name);
- Notes on other nearby colleges as well as pronunciation.

As far as we know, the data presented in this atlas is the most complete and accurate list of the forty College of Education currently in existence.

Satellite mapping to add buildings and roads

Once the locations of the colleges were known, the usual OpenStreetMap process could be used to trace satellite imagery. This was initially undertaken by the first author, usually choosing colleges visited personally, and gradually adding data (for example while travelling). However, this progressed slowly, and only led to additional data for a limited number of colleges.

Field mapping to determine college boundaries

In October 2016, the NCTE-led ICT survey of the colleges offered an opportunity to collect more accurate data. Prior to the survey, we produced maps suitable for annotation¹². During the survey visit to a particular college, basic geospatial information was collected. A college member would draw the boundary of the college on to the annotatable paper map, as well as label college buildings..

We were not able to process this data immediately, but in early 2017 we transferred the college boundaries onto OpenStreetMap. Many colleges have boundary walls, are bounded by roads, or there is other structures delineating the college; for most colleges the information from the ICT survey was thus just needed to locate the appropriate boundary on the satellite image, allowing the precise mapping from the satellite image. However, for some colleges there is no visible boundary, and in some cases college staff was not able to indicate a precise boundary in some directions (for instance in cases where the college leads onto open fields). Those segments of the boundary were mapped approximately.

The mapping of the college boundaries was a significant step, as it allowed us to invite others to map those precise areas, for example during so-called “mapathons”.

¹² See e.g. <http://fieldpapers.org/>

Mapathons to add buildings and roads

As the college mapping proceeded slowly, we decided to see whether we could work with the Cambridge (UK) mapathons, organised by Missing Maps. Normally these mapathons map according to global priorities, and there are always mapping tasks suitable for newcomers.

The colleges task is slightly more complex, as it utilises a variety of OpenStreetMap tags, and also utilises OpenStreetMap relations. It thus became an ideal “practice task” for more advanced mappers, and (based on the Cambridge mapathon experience) originated the idea of such practice tasks. They allow mapathon participants, who have gathered some experience, to progress towards more complex tasks, but in a fairly controlled environment. Because the task itself is low priority, it remains available for a while, allowing mappers to return to the task over time to practice their skills. This prepares such mappers for more advanced tasks, as they become available as higher priority tasks. In other words, it builds a group of mappers that is able to rapidly respond to more complex tasks, as these arise.

Another element of the practice tasks is validation. Mapping for Missing Maps has two stages: First, an area is mapped; then the area is validated by a separate person. Usually there is a scarcity of validators. One of the reasons for the practice tasks was thus also to allow mappers to build their skills as validators — again, within tasks that are lower priority, allowing a shallower learning curve.

The task for mapping the colleges on the HOT Task Manager is still available¹³, for those who are interested. With the task being available on the Task Manager, it also became possible for contributions from the wider Missing Maps community. However, the main work happened during several Cambridge mapathons (mid to late 2017), sometimes with Ghanaian volunteers mapping in parallel. The remaining validation was then undertaken by the authors.

Tracing building outlines from satellite data was greatly aided through the availability of DigitalGlobe imagery for mapping in OpenStreetMap (announced 9th May 2017). Some of the existing satellite imagery had been of poor quality, and the new DigitalGlobe imagery allowed us to fill the gaps.

Printing PDFs

OpenStreetMap site. Once the colleges were mapped and validated, we used the OpenStreetMap site to produce individual PDFs, with scales 1:4,000 and 1:2,000 for most colleges (when printed on A4 paper). For some colleges a map at 1:8000 was added, to show the full college area on one A4 sheet of paper. The output map scale depends on the viewport (set to 1685 x 1190 for our maps, with settings z=17 and input scale 1,2000), and the zoom factors (z=18 or 17, and 16 for the largest scale maps). The input map scale

¹³ <https://tasks.hotosm.org/project/3296>

affects label size (set to 1:1000, 1:2000 and 1:2850 in our cases). With these two settings, map pages were exported to PDF individually, and then collated.¹⁴

Other options. There are various options for printing, for instance including Field Papers¹⁵ (as above, which is particularly useful annotation), MyOSMatic¹⁶ (which offers a scale bar as well), as well as InkAtlas¹⁷, which we have compared below.

	API	Road width adjust	Scale bar	Scale setting	PDF output	PDF is vector	Multi-page	Free
OSM	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
Fieldpapers	<i>"can"</i> ¹⁸	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
inkatlas	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No
MapOSmatic	<i>Planned</i>	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes ¹⁹	Yes

InkAtlas has the advantage that the scale can be specified exactly (like the OSM site) and (at the time of writing) it is the only site that offers an API²⁰ (as part of the paid subscription). The InkAtlas team generously gave us free access to InkAtlas and the API, enabling us to produce the atlas pages using InkAtlas.

Document assembly

The introductory text for this atlas was collaboratively written in Google Docs and exported to PDF, then combined with the map PDFs to produce a single document. The PDF merge was produced with the community-version of Coherent PDF (cpdf).²¹

¹⁴ See http://bjohas.de/wiki/Maps/Exporting_PDF_from_OSM for details.

¹⁵ <http://fieldpapers.org/>

¹⁶ <http://maposmatic.osm-baustelle.de>

¹⁷ <https://inkatlas.com/>

¹⁸ See "Make a canned atlas template", <http://fieldpapers.org/make-canned-atlas-template>

¹⁹ At present MapOSmatic can only produce multi-page atlases covering reasonable areas. It does not seem to be possible to produce an atlas covering large areas, e.g. a road atlas of Ghana.

²⁰ <https://inkatlas.com/docs/>

²¹ <http://community.coherentpdf.com/>, <https://github.com/johnwhittington/cpdf-source>

Obtaining and using the data in this atlas

This geospatial atlas data is stored in OpenStreetMap, and is available to all users of OpenStreetMap. The college locations were also added to Google Maps, to make the colleges discoverable there.

Using the atlas data on a mobile device

There are several applications enable the convenient use of OpenStreetMap data, including using this data offline. This section contains a few images of using the college data in the Maps.Me²² app, which is available for both Android and iOS.

This image shows the whole of Ghana. The red dot indicates that a map update is available for download. If you already have Maps.Me installed, with an older data download, you should update.

This image shows the results of a search for “college of education”. The results can be viewed on a list, or shown on the map (see image). Each blue dot represents a college, that can be tapped for adding a bookmark, or route planning.

²² <https://maps.me/download/>

This image shows a route planned from Gbewaa College of Education, via Enchi College of Education, to Ada College of Education.

This image shows details of Nusrat Jahan Ahmadiyya College of Education. The details for every college (as also shown in the pages to follow) are available via Maps.Me.

Obtaining a copy of this atlas

The atlas itself and the data presented in these tables are available in digital format here at this url

<http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>

Details are on how data can be retrieved from the OpenStreetMap (for example via the OpenStreetMap API or the the Overpass API) are also available at the above URL.

Feedback and future efforts

The authors would love to hear from you! If you are just finding the atlas useful, if you have questions or suggestions, if you have spotted a mistake, if you want additional features to be added, or if you need help using the atlas at your college, please get in touch, using this form:

<http://bjohas.de/go/atlasfeedback>

The form requires an email address and optionally you can provide a phone number. We look forward to hearing from you.

There are many further tasks, including educational mapping and otherwise. In the area of college mapping, our data is reasonably complete at this point in time. For some colleges the outlines are certainly imprecise, and they will need amending. If you are staff or student at one of the colleges, please check your map, and get in touch.

Moreover, we have not yet labeled individual buildings, which makes for an ideal task for future mapathons. The present data will no doubt need to be amended. Also, the atlas only covers the 40 public colleges (as of mid-2017), and there are more colleges in transition, and data would need to be added as those colleges become public colleges. For instance, in September 2017, Al-Faruq College of Education was accredited by the National Accreditation Board. We know the college is located between Wenchi and Droboso²³, but did not have time to determine the missing data. If you are at Al-Faruq College of Education, or any of the other newly accredited colleges, do get in touch.

For the colleges, we also organised the Wikipedia entries²⁴ that were already available (4 colleges), we created Wikipedia pages for the remaining 36 colleges. The pages are basic at the moment (“stubs”), but they do provide another entry point for our data. By creating Wikipedia pages for a college, the college map becomes available in the WikiMiniAtlas²⁵, which is available directly from the corresponding Wikipedia page.

A similar mapping effort could be made for other educational institutions, such as other colleges (e.g. health) and indeed universities. However, an important future mapping task is to map schools. Initial efforts are being made in that area²⁶, but there is much more data that could be released or be added. Currently this data has not been widely added to OpenStreetMap, which would be helpful for public/offline access, as well as to offer a separate data store.

We hope that this atlas will inspire more contributions in these areas!

²³ Google Maps indicates the position here, but we have not been able to independently confirm the exact GPS coordinates:

<https://www.google.co.uk/maps/place/Al-faruq+College+Of+Education/@7.7108681,-2.1053232,459m>

²⁴ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_colleges_of_education_in_Ghana

²⁵ <https://meta.wikimedia.org/wiki/WikiMiniAtlas>

²⁶ <http://ghanaschoolsinfo.org/>

Appendix 1: Attribution

Licence for this atlas

This atlas as a whole is available under Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International.

Björn Haßler, Jacob Tetteh Akunor, Enock Seth Nyamador (2017). *An Atlas of The Forty Colleges of Education in Ghana*. Available under Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International. Available at <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

The inside front cover has further details on this licence, and the pages below explain licences for the maps. The licence means that you can share the whole atlas in any medium or format. For example, you can print it, email it to others or place it onto your website. You are also welcome to adapt the atlas, as long as you are mindful of the licence conditions (attribution, share alike), see inside cover.

Overall contributions

Much of the college data was collated by the first author, drawing on various sources. The early collection of data was inspired by T-TEL²⁷, supplemented by information from the National Council for Tertiary Education²⁸. The National Accreditation Board²⁹ listings were also helpful to validate our data. District / town information was checked against Statoids Districts of Ghana³⁰ and Wikipedia³¹.

Contributions via the HOTOSM tasks manager and OSM

The following users contributed to this project³² on the HOTOSM tasks manager:

CycleStreets, Enock4seth, Fraser Donaldson, Hannah F, Harry Wood, Paul David baron Von Weenraid, bgirardot, bjohas, fenfe1, tomad, tpf.

These are listed separately, because (e.g. for validation) they are not recorded within OpenStreetMap itself.

²⁷ See e.g. <http://www.t-tel.org/about/coes-network.html>.

²⁸ <http://ncte.edu.gh/>, <http://www.openstreetmap.org/way/339022390>

²⁹ <http://www.nab.gov.gh/public-colleges-of-education>

³⁰ <http://www.statoids.com/ygh.html>

³¹ <http://www.wikipedia.org>

³² <https://tasks.hotosm.org/project/3296>

Mapathons in the UK were supported by the first author, while the third author coordinated mapathons in Ghana. The Ghana postcodes³³ were generated by Patrick Agyei (Youth Mapper, UMAT).

Further contributions were made by OpenStreetMap users directly via OpenStreetMap, particularly prior to our project. This information is available on OpenStreetMap.

The Inkatlas team³⁴ generously gave us free access to Inkatlas and the API, enabling us to produce atlas pages using Inkatlas.

Contributions to Wikipedia

The first and third author also created pages for 36 colleges on Wikipedia; only 4 already had pages on Wikipedia, which were amended as needed. Wikipedia automatically loads data from OpenStreetMap to generate the WikiMiniAtlas, which means that the map data is also available via Wikipedia.

Akrokerri College of Education

From Wikipedia, the free encyclopedia

Akrokerri College of Education is a teacher education college in Akrokerri (Adansi West District, Ashanti Region, Ghana).^[1] The college is located in Ashanti / Brong Ahafo zone. It is one of the **about 40 public colleges of education in Ghana**.^[2] The college participated in the DFID-funded T-TEL programme.^[3]

Akrokerri College of Education

Affiliation	Government of Ghana
Location	Akrokerri, Adansi West District, A22020, Ghana
	6.30061°N 1.64885°W﻿ / ﻿6.30061°N 1.64885°W﻿ / ﻿6.30061; -1.64885﻿ / ﻿6.30061; -1.64885

References

- ↑ *^* *a* *b* Björn Ha An Atlas of T Creative Com <http://bjohas.d>
- ↑ National Ac
- ↑ "Our netwo Ghana. Retri

V · T · E
Ashanti
Central
Eastern
Greater Accra
Northern
Upper West
Volta
Western

³³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Postal_codes_in_Ghana

³⁴ <https://inkatlas.com/>

Appendix 2: College data

The data presented in these tables is also available in digital format (see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>). It is licensed under the Open Database License (details below). The first double page contains:

- **College Name (official).** The full official college name.
- **Zone / Region / District / Municipal / Metropolitan / Town.** The physical location of the college. This is not the postal address (usually a PO box); those are readily available from the NAB site.
- **College name (usual).** Often the full college name is slightly shortened, to produce the usual name of the college.
- **Nickname.** All colleges have a nickname/acronym, provided here.
- **Notes.** For some colleges there are brief notes on variants in the name and pronunciation; nearby colleges are also indicated.

The second double page contains:

- **Location (WGS84).** GPS coordinates of the visual centre of the college.
- **Google map area.** Google maps link to the GPS coordinates.
- **Google map search.** Google maps search for college name, to verify that the college is discoverable on google maps.
- **Location link (Google).** Google maps link to college and coordinates, to provide a good view of the college in Google Maps.
- **OSM relation.** The number of the college 'relation' on OpenStreetMap. The relation groups all college-related objects together, useful for performing statistical analysis on the OSM data.
- **OSM relation link.** Link to OpenStreetMap relation, for inspection.
- **JOSM edit link.** Link for editing the OpenStreetMap relation in JOSM.
- **Open Location Code (full).** The full Open Location Code.
- **"Plus code" URL.** Link to <https://plus.codes>, to view the OLC in relation to nearby OLCs. College may wish to adopt an OLC that points to the main administrative building or the college entrance.
- **Google map, full OLC.** Search on Google Map for the code, to show how the code can be utilised.
- **One degree prefix.** The first four characters of the code, which corresponds to a one degree area (100km at the equator.)
- **Short Open Location Code.** An OLC can be shortened by providing a reference to a nearby town. E.g. for "6FV2CF68+QR", the one degree prefix "6FV2" can be dropped if the town is included, i.e. "CF68+QR Jasikan, Ghana". This provides a postcode-like system.
- **Google map, short OLC.** Google Map search to verify the short OLC
- **Ghana postcode.** In 2017, Ghana introduced a postcode system. Those postcodes are provided for reference.

#	College Name (official)	Zone	Region	District / Municipal / Metropolitan
1	Abetifi Presbyterian College of Education	Eastern / Greater Accra	Eastern	Kwahu East
2	Accra College of Education	Eastern / Greater Accra	Greater Accra	Accra Metro
3	Ada College of Education	Eastern / Greater Accra	Greater Accra	Ada East
4	Agogo Presbyterian College of Education	Ashanti / Brong Ahafo	Ashanti	Ashanti-Akin North
5	Akatsi College of Education	Volta Zone	Volta Region	Akatsi South
6	Akrokerrri College of Education	Ashanti / Brong Ahafo	Ashanti	Adansi West
7	Atebubu College of Education	Ashanti / Brong Ahafo	Brong-Ahafo	Atebubu Amanten
8	Bagabaga College of Education	Northern Zone	Northern Region	Sagnarigu
9	Berekum College of Education	Ashanti / Brong Ahafo	Brong-Ahafo	Berekum Municipal
10	Dambai College of Education	Volta Zone	Volta Region	Krachi East
11	Enchi College of Education	Central / Western	Western	Aowin District
12	Evangelical Presbyterian College of Education, Amedzofe	Volta Zone	Volta Region	Ho West
13	Evangelical Presbyterian College of Education, Bimbilla	Northern Zone	Northern Region	Nanumba North
14	Foso College of Education	Central / Western	Central	Assin North Municipal
15	Gambaga College of Education	Northern Zone	Northern Region	East Mamprusi
16	Gbewaa College of Education	Northern Zone	Northern Region	Pusiga
17	Holy Child College of Education	Central / Western	Western	Sekondi Takoradi Metro
18	Jasikan College of Education	Volta Zone	Volta Region	Jasikan
19	Kibi Presbyterian College of Education	Eastern / Greater Accra	Eastern	East Akim Municipal
20	Komenda College of Education	Central / Western	Central	Komenda-Edina-Eguafo-Abirem Municipal
21	Mampong Technical College of Education	Ashanti / Brong Ahafo	Ashanti	Mampong Municipal
22	Mount Mary College of Education	Eastern / Greater Accra	Eastern	Yilo Krobo
23	Nusrat Jahan Ahmadiyya College of Education	Northern Zone	Upper West	WA Municipal
24	Offinso College of Education	Ashanti / Brong Ahafo	Ashanti	Offinso South
25	Our Lady of Apostles College of Education	Central / Western	Central	Cape Coast Municipal
26	Peki College of Education	Volta Zone	Volta Region	South Dayi
27	Presbyterian College of Education, Akropong	Eastern / Greater Accra	Eastern	Akwapim North Municipal
28	Presbyterian Women's College of Education, Aburi	Eastern / Greater Accra	Eastern	Akuapem South
29	Seventh Day Adventist College of Education	Eastern / Greater Accra	Eastern	New Juaben Municipal
30	St. Ambrose College of Education	Ashanti / Brong Ahafo	Brong-Ahafo	Dormaa Municipal
31	St. Francis College of Education	Volta Zone	Volta Region	Hohoe Municipal
32	St. John Bosco's College of Education	Northern Zone	Upper East	Kassena Nankana East
33	St. Joseph's College of Education	Ashanti / Brong Ahafo	Brong-Ahafo	Tano North
34	St. Louis College of Education	Ashanti / Brong Ahafo	Ashanti	Kumasi Metro
35	St. Monica's College of Education	Ashanti / Brong Ahafo	Ashanti	Mampong Municipal
36	St. Teresa's College of Education	Volta Zone	Volta Region	Hohoe Municipal
37	Tamale College of Education	Northern Zone	Northern Region	Sagnarigu
38	Tumu College of Education	Northern Zone	Upper West	Sissala East
39	Wesley College of Education	Ashanti / Brong Ahafo	Ashanti	Kumasi Metro
40	Wiawso College of Education	Central / Western	Western	Sefwi-Wiawso Municipal

#	Town	College name (usual)	Nickname	Notes
1	Abetifi-Kwahu	Abetifi Presby College of Education	Abetico	We have seen the district listed as "Kwahu North", but believe this to be incorrect or outdated.
2	Accra	-	Atraco	
3	Ada-Foah	-	AdaCo	
4	Agogo	-	APCE	
5	Akatsi	-	Akatsico	
6	Akrokkerri	-	Adansi University	
7	Atebubu	-	Ateco	
8	Tamale	-	Bace / Batco	Tamale CoE nearby.
9	Berekum	-	Betco	
10	Dambai	-	Dace	
11	Enchi	-	Enchico	
12	Amedzofe	E. P. College of Education, Amedzofe	Ameco	
13	Bimbilla	E. P. College of Education, Bimbilla	Bimbico	
14	Foso	-	Fosco	
15	Gambaga	-	Gatco	
16	Pusiga-Bawku	-	-	
17	Takoradi	-	Holico	
18	Jasikan-Buem	-	Bodyco	
19	Kibi	-	Kibicoe	
20	Komenda	-	Komenco	
21	Mampong (Ashanti)	-	Mamtech	St. Monica's CoE nearby.
22	Somanya	Mt. Mary College of Education	MomaCo	
23	Wa	N. J. Ahmadiyya College of Education	NJA	
24	Offinso	-	Offinco	
25	Cape Coast	OLA College of Education	Ola	
26	Peki	-	Govco	
27	Akropong-Akuapem	-	Presby PTC	
28	Aburi	Presby Women's College of Education	Aburi PWCE	Aburi is pronounced "eh-BREE" not "Ah-BOO-ree"; districted also referred to as "Kwapim South".
29	Asokore	SDA College of Education	SedaCo	Located near Koforidua.
30	Dormaa Akwamu	-	SACE	
31	Hohoe	-	Franco	St. Teresa CoE nearby.
32	Navrongo	-	Bosco	District sometimes listed "Navrongo Central", but we believe this to be incorrect or outdated.
33	Bechem	-	Josco	
34	Kumasi	-	-	Wesley CoE nearby.
35	Mampong (Ashanti)	-	Monico	Mampong Tech nearby.
36	Hohoe	-	Teresco / Wotraco	St. Francis CoE nearby.
37	Tamale	-	TaCo / Tace	Bagabaga CoE nearby.
38	Tumu	-	Tutco	
39	Kumasi	-	Wesco	St. Joseph's CoE nearby.
40	Sefwi-Wiawso	-	Watico	Pronounced se-fwee-YAW-soo

#	College Name	Location (WGS84)	Gg. map area	Gg. map search	Loc. link (Gg.)	OSM relation	OSM rel. link
1	Abetifi Presbyterian College of Education	6.66639,-0.73969	link	link	link	7063737	link
2	Accra College of Education	5.65719,-0.16094	link	link	link	7062402	link
3	Ada College of Education	5.78044,0.62001	link	link	link	7062156	link
4	Agogo Presbyterian College of Education	6.79320,-1.08847	link	link	link	7063755	link
5	Akatsi College of Education	6.12562,0.80077	link	link	link	7063159	link
6	Akrokerry College of Education	6.30061,-1.64885	link	link	link	7063752	link
7	Atebubu College of Education	7.73314,-0.99757	link	link	link	7063753	link
8	Bagabaga College of Education	9.42393,-0.86935	link	link	link	7063744	link
9	Berekum College of Education	7.44510,-2.57545	link	link	link	7063749	link
10	Dambai College of Education	8.06568,0.17651	link	link	link	6684343	link
11	Enchi College of Education	5.82944,-2.82522	link	link	link	7062034	link
12	E. P. College of Education, Amedzofe	6.84324,0.43728	link	link	link	7063741	link
13	E. P. College of Education, Bimbilla	8.87150,0.04833	link	link	link	7063743	link
14	Foso College of Education	5.68330,-1.26489	link	link	link	7062559	link
15	Gambaga College of Education	10.53137,-0.43301	link	link	link	7063756	link
16	Gbewaa College of Education	11.06708,-0.11491	link	link	link	7063745	link
17	Holy Child College of Education	4.93675,-1.74721	link	link	link	7063665	link
18	Jasikan College of Education	7.4125,0.4631	link	link	link	7063739	link
19	Kibi Presbyterian College of Education	6.15412,-0.56171	link	link	link	7061989	link
20	Komenda College of Education	5.04632,-1.50526	link	link	link	7063746	link
21	Mampong Technical College of Education	7.05752,-1.39069	link	link	link	6683729	link
22	Mount Mary College of Education	6.11552,-0.01543	link	link	link	7062379	link
23	Nusrat Jahan Ahmadiyya College of Education	10.06669,-2.48125	link	link	link	7063742	link
24	Offinso College of Education	6.94795,-1.68230	link	link	link	7063751	link
25	Our Lady of Apostles College of Education	5.10478,-1.27401	link	link	link	7063748	link
26	Peki College of Education	6.51585,0.21549	link	link	link	7062056	link
27	Presbyterian College of Education, Akropong	5.98050,-0.09046	link	link	link	7063738	link
28	Presbyterian Women's College of Education	5.85002,-0.17457	link	link	link	7061952	link
29	Seventh Day Adventist College of Education	6.11809,-0.27649	link	link	link	7063736	link
30	St. Ambrose College of Education	7.30736,-2.73869	link	link	link	7063757	link
31	St. Francis College of Education	7.15794,0.49038	link	link	link	7062476	link
32	St. John Bosco's College of Education	10.87306,-1.07791	link	link	link	7062542	link
33	St. Joseph's College of Education	7.08108,-2.02379	link	link	link	7063750	link
34	St. Louis College of Education	6.70723,-1.62540	link	link	link	7062564	link
35	St. Monica's College of Education	7.04674,-1.40314	link	link	link	7063754	link
36	St. Teresa's College of Education	7.15879,0.48193	link	link	link	6684551	link
37	Tamale College of Education	9.42136,-0.85926	link	link	link	7063222	link
38	Tumu College of Education	10.89266,-1.98463	link	link	link	7062539	link
39	Wesley College of Education	6.7144,-1.6229	link	link	link	7062482	link
40	Wiawso College of Education	6.19757,-2.49140	link	link	link	7063747	link

#	JOSM edit link	Open Locaton Code (full)	Plus codes URL	Gg. map, full OLC	one deg. prefix	Short Open Location Code	Gg. map, short OLC	Ghana postcode
1	link	6CRXM786+V9	link	link	6CRX	M786+V9 Abetifi, Ghana	link	EH0024
2	link	6CQXMR4P+QV	link	link	6CQX	MR4P+QV Accra, Ghana	link	GA516
3	link	6FQ2QJJ9+CX	link	link	6FQ2	QJJ9+CX Ada-Foah, Ghana	link	GY0294
4	link	6CRWQWV7+H6	link	link	6CRW	QWV7+H6 Agogo, Ghana	link	AN0006
5	link	6FR24RG2+6P	link	link	6FR2	4RG2+6P Akatsi, Ghana	link	VX0007
6	link	6CRW8922+59	link	link	6CRW	8922+59 Akrokerri, Ghana	link	A22020
7	link	6CVXP2M3+72	link	link	6CVX	P2M3+72 Atebubu, Ghana	link	BA00070
8	link	6CXXC4FJ+MF	link	link	6CXX	C4FJ+MF Tamale, Ghana	link	NS002
9	link	6CVVCCVF+RF	link	link	6CVV	CCVF+RF Berekum, Ghana	link	BB0023
10	link	6FW2358G+37	link	link	6FW2	358G+37 Dambai, Ghana	link	VR00006
11	link	6CQVR5HF+HJ	link	link	6CQV	R5HF+HJ Enchi, Ghana	link	WA00004
12	link	6FR2RCVP+7R	link	link	6FR2	RCVP+7R Ho Municipality, Ghana	link	V10523
13	link	6FW2V372+6W	link	link	6FW2	V372+6W Bimbilla, Ghana	link	NN0031
14	link	6CQWMPMP+79	link	link	6CQW	MPMP+79 Foso, Ghana	link	CR0074
15	link	7C2XGHJ8+XF	link	link	7C2X	GHJ8+XF Gambaga, Ghana	link	NE0001
16	link	7C3X3V8P+Q9	link	link	7C3X	3V8P+Q9 Pusiga-Bawku, Ghana	link	UP0085
17	link	6CPWW7P3+9X	link	link	6CPW	W7P3+9X Takoradi, Ghana	link	WS124
18	link	6FV2CF68+QR	link	link	6FV2	CF68+QR Jasikan, Ghana	link	VJ0005
19	link	6CRX5C3Q+J8	link	link	6CRX	5C3Q+J8 Kibi, Ghana	link	EE0051
20	link	6CQW2FVV+PQ	link	link	6CQW	2FVV+PQ Komenda, Ghana	link	CK1838
21	link	6CVW3H3X+8X	link	link	6CVW	3H3X+8X Mampong, Ghana	link	AM0024
22	link	6CRX4X8M+5M	link	link	6CRX	4X8M+5M Somanya, Ghana	link	EY0030
23	link	7C2V3G89+37	link	link	7C2V	3G89+37 Wa, Ghana	link	XW0051
24	link	6CRWW8X9+56	link	link	6CRW	W8X9+56 Offinso, Ghana	link	A70014
25	link	6CQW4P3G+JF	link	link	6CQW	4P3G+JF Cape Coast, Ghana	link	CC101
26	link	6FR2G688+9F	link	link	6FR2	G688+9F South Dayi, Ghana	link	VE1103
27	link	6CQXXWH5+MW	link	link	6CQX	XWH5+MW Akropong, Ghana	link	E20004
28	link	6CQXRRXG+Q9	link	link	6CQX	RRXG+Q9 Aburi, Ghana	link	E3003
29	link	6CRX4P9F+FC	link	link	6CRX	4P9F+FC Koforidua, Ghana	link	EN182
30	link	6CVV8746+G7	link	link	6CVV	8746+G7 Dormaa Akwamu, Ghana	link	BE0255
31	link	6FV25F5R+67	link	link	6FV2	5F5R+67 Hohoe, Ghana	link	VC0026
32	link	7C2WVWFF+C4	link	link	7C2W	VWFF+C4 Navrongo, Ghana	link	UK0114
33	link	6CVV3XJG+G6	link	link	6CVV	3XJG+G6 Bechem, Ghana	link	B30021
34	link	6CRWP94F+QF	link	link	6CRW	P94F+QF Kumasi, Ghana	link	AK015
35	link	6CVW2HWW+GH	link	link	6CVW	2HWW+GH Mampong, Ghana	link	AM0069
36	link	6FV25F5J+JM	link	link	6FV2	5F5J+JM Hohoe, Ghana	link	VC0002
37	link	6CXXC4CQ+HG	link	link	6CXX	C4CQ+HG Tamale, Ghana	link	NS046
38	link	7C2WV2V8+J6	link	link	7C2W	V2V8+J6 Tumu, Ghana	link	XS00091
39	link	6CRWP97G+8C	link	link	6CRW	P97G+8C Kumasi, Ghana	link	AK014
40	link	6CRV5GX5+29	link	link	6CRV	5GX5+29 Sefwi-Wiawso, Ghana	link	WG0020

Licence for the college data

The data presented in these tables is also available in digital format (see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>). Our data collection and the content is licensed as follows:

These list of data for the Colleges of Education (Ghana) is made available under the Open Database License:

<http://opendatacommons.org/licenses/odbl/1.0/>. Any rights in individual

contents of the database are licensed under the Database Contents License:

<http://opendatacommons.org/licenses/dbcl/1.0/>.

Note in particular that the licences assert that factual information is not covered by copyright. The Contents are licensed by the Licensor “as is” and without any warranty of any kind.

Under this licence, **you are free:**

- **To Share:** To copy, distribute and use the database.
- **To Create:** To produce works from the database.
- **To Adapt:** To modify, transform and build upon the database.

As long as you:

- **Attribute:** You must attribute any public use of the database, or works produced from the database, in the manner specified in the ODbL. For any use or redistribution of the database, or works produced from it, you must make clear to others the license of the database and keep intact any notices on the original database.
- **Share-Alike:** If you publicly use any adapted version of this database, or works produced from an adapted database, you must also offer that adapted database under the ODbL.
- **Keep open:** If you redistribute the database, or an adapted version of it, then you may use technological measures that restrict the work (such as DRM) as long as you also redistribute a version without such measures.

Disclaimer

This text is not a license. It is simply a handy reference for understanding the ODbL 1.0 — it is a human-readable expression of some of its key terms. This document has no legal value, and its contents do not appear in the actual license. Read the full [ODbL 1.0 license text](#) for the exact terms that apply.

Appendix 3: Overview map of the colleges

The following double page provides an overview of the locations of the 40 colleges. Alternative versions of this map (including different colour schemes) are available at <http://bjoahas.de/atlas2017>.

Created on Inkatlas. © OpenStreetMap contributors (openstreetmap.org), Inkatlas. Map data Oct 27, 2017. 1:2000000

Created on Inkatlas. © OpenStreetMap contributors (openstreetmap.org), Inkatlas. Map data Oct 27, 2017. 1:2000000

Licence for the overview map

You should not the following licence terms:

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL).

The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>.

And the following notes:

The PDFs were produced using the <https://inkatlas.com/> API. For further information, and for attribution, use <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Appendix 4: College maps

The following pages contain maps of all forty colleges. The scales are 1:4,000 and 1:2,000 (where two maps are present). For some larger colleges, a view at 1:8,000 is also included (plus a fourth map, either at 1:4,000 or 1:2,000) to maintain sets of 2 or 4 maps.

On each page, underneath the college name, coordinates are provided in the format

zoom/lat/lon, e.g. 17/6.66639/-0.73969

which can be used to locate the area on OpenStreetMap, e.g.

<http://www.openstreetmap.org/#map=17/6.66639/-0.73969>

Underneath the coordinates, the scale is provided (when printed on A4), as well as the area covered by a full A4 sheet (1:2,000 → 542m x 420m; 1:4,000 → 1,084m x 840m; 1:8,000 → 2,168m x 1,680m). In other words, the actual distance left-to-right on an A4 landscape page (271mm) is roughly 0.5 km, 1 km and 2km.

Each page is built from with scalable vector data. This enables large scale printing for individual pages for college use. For large scale printing (e.g. on A3 or A2, the scale is reduced accordingly).

Licence for the college maps

You should not the following licence terms:

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL).

The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>.

And the following notes:

The PDFs were produced using the <https://inkatlas.com/> API. For further information, and for attribution, use <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

The license terms are printed in each page, which means that you can extract single pages and print and share them digitally, without needed to add further attribution.

Abetifi Presbyterian College of Education

17/6.66639/-0.73969

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

Abetifi
Presbyterian
College
of Education

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Abetifi Presbyterian College of Education

18/6.66639/-0.73969

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Accra College of Education

17/5.65719/-0.16094

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Accra College of Education

18/5.65793/-0.16102

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Ada College of Education

17/5.78044/0.62001

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Ada College of Education

18/5.78035/0.61990

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Agogo Presbyterian College of Education

17/6.79320/-1.08847

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Agogo Presbyterian College of Education

18/6.79320/-1.08847

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Akatsi College of Education

17/6.12562/0.80077

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Akatsi College of Education

18/6.12565/0.80128

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Akrokerri College of Education

17/6.30135/-1.64837

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Akrokerri College of Education

18/6.30133/-1.64917

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

IR6

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Atebubu College of Education

17/7.73378/-0.99704

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Atebubu College of Education

18/7.73314/-0.99757

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Bagabaga College of Education

16/9.4224/-0.8637

2,168m x 1,680m, 1:8,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODBL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Bagabaga College of Education

17/9.42226/-0.86744

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Bagabaga College of Education

17/9.42504/-0.86790

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Bagabaga College of Education

18/9.42478/-0.86980

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Berekum College of Education

17/7.44510/-2.57545

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Berekum College of Education

18/7.44408/-2.57508

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Dambai College of Education

16/8.0635/0.1746

2,168m x 1,680m, 1:8,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Dambai College of Education

17/8.06568/0.17651

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

Dambai
College
of Education

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Dambai College of Education

18/8.06561/0.17651

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Dambai College of Education

18/8.06319/0.17633

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

Dambai
College
of Education

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Enchi College of Education

17/5.82944/-2.82522

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Enchi College of Education

18/5.82896/-2.82508

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

*Enchi College
of Education*

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Evangelical Presbyterian College of Education, Amedzofe

17/6.84324/0.43728

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Evangelical Presbyterian College of Education, Amedzofe

18/6.84289/0.43741

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Evangelical Presbyterian College of Education, Bimbilla

16/8.87150/0.04833

2,168m x 1,680m, 1:8,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Evangelical Presbyterian College of Education, Bimbilla

17/8.87150/0.04833

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Evangelical Presbyterian College of Education, Bimbilla

18/8.87150/0.04833

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

*Evangelical
Presbyterian
College
of Education,
Bimbilla*

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Evangelical Presbyterian College of Education, Bimbilla

18/8.87443/0.04442

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Foso College of Education

17/5.68300/-1.26500

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Foso College of Education

18/5.68330/-1.26489

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Gambaga College of Education

17/10.53137/-0.43301

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Gambaga College of Education

18/10.53137/-0.43301

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Gbewaa College of Education

17/11.06708/-0.11491

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Gbewaa College of Education

18/11.06708/-0.11491

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

Gbewaa
College
of Education

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Holy Child College of Education

17/4.93675/-1.74721

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

Holy Child
College
of Education

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Holy Child College of Education

18/4.93645/-1.74720

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

Holy Child
College
of Education

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Jasikan College of Education

16/7.41225/0.46242

2,168m x 1,680m, 1:8,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Jasikan College of Education

17/7.41225/0.46242

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Jasikan College of Education

Jasikan
College
of Education

18/7.41087/0.46445

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Jasikan College of Education

18/7.41323/0.46441

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

*Jasikan
College
of Education*

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Kibi Presbyterian College of Education

17/6.15412/-0.56171

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Kibi Presbyterian College of Education

18/6.15412/-0.56146

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

Kibi Presbyterian
College
of Education

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Komenda College of Education

17/5.04618/-1.50581

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Komenda College of Education

18/5.04641/-1.50562

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

Komenda
College
of Education

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Mampong Technical College of Education

17/7.05690/-1.39080

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Mampong Technical College of Education

18/7.05772/-1.39088

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Mount Mary College of Education

17/6.11552/-0.01543

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Mount Mary College of Education

18/6.11552/-0.01543

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Nusrat Jahan Ahmadiyya College of Education

17/10.06691/-2.48058

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Nusrat Jahan Ahmadiyya College of Education

18/10.06691/-2.48058

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Offinso College of Education

16/6.9495/-1.6824

2,168m x 1,680m, 1:8,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Offinso College of Education

17/6.94795/-1.68230

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Offinso College of Education

18/6.94680/-1.68318

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Offinso College of Education

18/6.94868/-1.68170

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

Offinso
College
of Education

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Our Lady of Apostles College of Education

16/5.1048/1.2740
2,168m x 1 680m, 1:8,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Our Lady of Apostles College of Education

17/5.10404/-1.27390

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Our Lady of Apostles College of Education

18/5.10482/-1.27350

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Our Lady of Apostles College of Education

18/5.10656/-1.27387

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Peki College of Education

17/6.51585/0.21549

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

Peki College
of Education

A detailed map of the Peki College of Education campus. The campus is outlined in yellow and contains numerous brown rectangular buildings of various sizes. A network of white roads is shown, with a central road labeled 'Peki College of Education'. A red dashed line indicates a specific path or boundary within the campus. A large green area, likely a field or sports field, is located in the lower right quadrant. The campus is bordered by a grey area, and a prominent orange road labeled 'N2' runs along the right side. The map is oriented with the top-left corner of the campus at the top of the page.

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Peki College of Education

18/6.51585/0.21549

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

Peki College
of Education

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Presbyterian College of Education, Akropong

17/5.98050/-0.09046

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Presbyterian College of Education, Akropong

18/5.98050/-0.09046

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Presbyterian Women's College of Education, Aburi

17/5.85002/-0.17457

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Presbyterian Women's College of Education, Aburi

18/5.85002/-0.17457

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Seventh Day Adventist College of Education

17/6:11809/-0.27649

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Seventh Day Adventist College of Education

18/6.11809/-0.27649

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

SDA College
of Education

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

St. Ambrose College of Education

17/7.30673/-2.73839

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

St. Ambrose
College
of Education

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

St. Ambrose College of Education

18/7.30736/-2.73869

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

*St. Ambrose
College
of Education*

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

St. Francis College of Education

17/7.15794/0.49038

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

St. Francis College of Education

18/7.15794/0.49038

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

St. Francis
Demonstration

St. Francis
College
of Education

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

St. John Bosco's College of Education

17/10.87300/-1.07689

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

St. John Bosco's College of Education

18/10.87306/-1.07791

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

St. Joseph's College of Education

17/7.08059/-2.02372

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

St. Joseph's College of Education

18/7.08108/-2.02379

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

St. Louis College of Education

17/6.70723/-1.62540

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

St. Louis College of Education

18/6.70723/-1.62540

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

Asanteman
Secondary
School

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

St. Monica's College of Education

17/7.04674/-1.40314

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

St. Monica's College of Education

18/7.04674/-1.40314

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

St. Teresa's College of Education

17/7.15879/0.48193

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

St. Teresa's College of Education

18/7.15879/0.48193

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Tamale College of Education

17/9.42111/-0.85911

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Tamale College of Education

Dormitory
18/9.42136/-0.85926
542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Tumu College of Education

16/10.89266/-1.98463

2,168m x 1,680m, 1:8,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Tumu College of Education

17/10.89266/-1.98463

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Tumu College of Education

18/10.89121/-1.98475

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Tumu College of Education

18/10.89337/-1.98478

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Wesley College of Education

16/6.7128/-1.6230

2,168m x 1,680m, 1:8,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Wesley College of Education

17/6.7144/-1.6229

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Wesley College of Education

18/6.71349/-1.62359

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Wesley College of Education

18/6.71566/-1.62219

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Wiawso College of Education

17/6.19762/-2.49217

1,084m x 840m, 1:4,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

Wiawso College of Education

18/6.19757/-2.49140

542m x 420m, 1:2,000 on A4

This map was produced using OpenStreetMap®. The copyright of the data for this map belongs to the OpenStreetMap contributors. The data is made available as open data (under the Open Data Commons Open Database License) by the OpenStreetMap Foundation. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our data, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our data, you may distribute the result only under the same licence (ODbL). The cartography is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 2.0 license. **You are free to copy, distribute, transmit and adapt our maps, as long as you credit OpenStreetMap and its contributors.** If you alter or build upon our maps, you may distribute the result only under the same Creative Commons licence. The full legal code explains your rights and responsibilities, see <http://www.openstreetmap.org/copyright>. About the CoE Atlas, see <http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>.

<http://bjohas.de/atlas2017>